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Research Paper

Formulation And Evaluation of a Charcoal-Based Cream for Psoriasis Management

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ABSTRACT

To investigate the efficacy of a charcoal-based cream in managing psoriasis symptoms and improving skin health through topical application. Activated charcoal and other excipients were used to prepare various cream formulations, which were evaluated for pH, spreadability, viscosity, washability, and antimicrobial activity using standard pharmaceutical techniques. Five trial formulations were developed and evaluated, with formulation F5 demonstrating optimal physical, chemical, and antimicrobial properties. Antimicrobial testing showed significant inhibition against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Candida albicans*. The optimized charcoal-based cream shows promise as an effective topical therapy for psoriasis management.

INTRODUCTION

Psoriasis, a chronic autoimmune skin disorder, affects approximately 2-3% of the global population, imposing significant physical and psychological burdens on patients. Its characteristic symptoms include red, inflamed patches of skin covered with silvery scales, often accompanied by itching, pain, and discomfort. Psoriasis is a common inflammatory and chronic skin disease affecting both men and women. Its prevalence in India ranges from 0.44 to 2.8%. The proportion of psoriasis was found to be 2.6% out

of all skin diseases [1]. A person's genetic makeup can also be the reason for the development of this disease [2]. Its beginning involves T cells (a type of WBC), immune system sends such signals that put T cells in action and become overly active, which leads to unhealthy swelling and fast turnover of skin cells. Although any part of the body can be affected but knees, elbows, knuckles, lower back and sacral areas are most commonly affected [3]. Breaking, pitting, thickening of the nail or thickening under the nails are the symptoms of Nail psoriasis which is the rarest type of Psoriasis. Around 20% of people with psoriasis are

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suffering from psoriatic arthritis which is very painful [4]. It is an incurable disease, only symptomatically relief can be achieved and severity can be lessened. Symptoms can be cleared for months or even years but it is a lifelong disease [5]. Affected skin is itchy and irritating, people suffering from psoriasis may also suffer from Type-2 diabetes, inflammatory bowel disease, cardiovascular disease, psoriatic arthritis and microbial skin infections. On the basis of severity, location, duration, shape, size and pattern of scales, psoriasis can be classified into the following types: Pustular erythrodermic, inverse, guttate, plaque, psoriatic, nail and scalp psoriasis. Researchers around the world have identified several areas on the human genome where more than one gene may be involved in psoriasis and psoriatic arthritis [6]. More recent studies have suggested multiple loci on many different chromosomes besides chromosome 6, including chromosomes 1, 2, 4, 8, 16, 5, and 20 [7-14]. While there seem to be multiple genes that contribute to the psoriatic phenotype, most investigators focus on the MHC (Major Histocompatibility Complex) I region, with particular interest on the Human Leukocyte [HLA-Cw6] Antigen allele [15]. Localization of a second psoriasis susceptibility locus (PSORS2) to chromosome 17q25 was achieved following a genome-wide linkage scan on eight multiply affected families [16]. Psoriasis is an autoimmune inflammatory disease that causes the cells of the last layer of the skin, keratinocytes, to grow much faster than normal, every three or four days instead of 28 days, as happens with the cells of a healthy person, leading to psoriatic. This disease affects almost 138 million people worldwide, the prevalence of this type of disease worldwide is around 2–3%, causes itching or painful patches of thickened skin, reddened with silvery scales that appear on different parts of the body [17].

This disease does not respect factors of age, sex, origin, socioeconomic or cultural, its maximum incidence is between 20 and 50 years [18]. The cause of psoriasis is unclear, but it is known to involve immune stimulation of epidermal keratinocytes; T cells appear to play a central role. Family history is common, and some human leukocyte genes and antigens (Cw6, B13, B17) have been associated with psoriasis [19].

CAUSES OF PSORIASIS

The cause of psoriasis is not fully understood, but there are several factors responsible which include genetics, environmental factors and the immune system.

Genetics

It plays a major role in the development of this disease. Approximately 10% of the general population have genes which are predisposed to psoriasis; but out of 10% only 1-3% of the populations develop the disease. Family with history of psoriasis have higher chance to develop this disease. Identical twin studies suggested a 70% chance of a twin developing psoriasis, if the other twin has the disease. The chance of developing disease is 20% in case of non-identical twin. These studies suggests both genetic and environmental factors are responsible in developing psoriasis [20].

Environmental factors

Certain environmental factors trigger the psoriasis gene to become active. Some of the factors are:

Infections, such as streptococcal throat or skin infections, injury to the skin, such as a cut or scrape, severe sunburn, and other factors like weather, smoking, and alcohol consumption can trigger psoriasis.

For example, some people with psoriasis might experience a flare-up after a cut or scrape, or if they get a severe sunburn. Similarly, infections like strep throat or skin infections can also trigger the condition. Other potential triggers include weather changes (especially cold and dry conditions), smoking, heavy alcohol consumption, and certain medications like lithium or high blood pressure drugs.

- Stress
- Cold weather
- Smoking
- Obesity
- Heavy alcohol consumption
- Folate and vitamin B12 deficiency
- Certain medications like lithium, which is prescribed for bipolar disorder; high blood pressure medications such as beta blockers and antimalarial drugs [21].

Co-morbidities of Psoriasis

Psoriasis is associated with high morbidity and great level of psychological stress.

The co-morbidities of psoriasis are:

- Psoriasis arthritis
- Cardiovascular disease and metabolic syndrome
- Crohn's disease
- Cancer

CREAM

Creams are the semisolid dosage forms that are intended for topical application to the skin, placement on the surface of the eye, or usage

nasally, vaginally, or rectally for medicinal, protective, or cosmetic activity. These preparations are utilised for localised effects caused by medication penetration into the underlying layer of skin or mucous membrane at the place of application. These items are intended to deliver drugs into the skin in order to treat dermal ailments, with the skin serving as the target organ. Creams are oil-and-water emulsions that are semi-solid. They are classified into two types: Oil-in water (O/W) creams, which are made up of small droplets of oil spread in a continuous phase, and water-in-oil (W/O) creams, which are made up of small droplets of water dispersed in an oily phase.

Classification of Cream on the Basis of Function

- Cleansing and cold cream
- Foundation and vanishing cream
- Night and massage cream
- Head and body cream
- All purpose and general cream

All-purpose cream act as nourishing night creams when applied exclusively, they function as hand cream when applied sparingly, and thus they are called as All-purpose cream. It is used by sports men or skilling or outdoor activities. "All-purpose cream" often refers to a multi-functional beauty product designed to give a number of advantages for the skin and, in some cases, other sections of the body in the context of cosmetics and skincare. These creams are designed to address a variety of skincare conditions and may have numerous functions. The ingredients and features of such creams can differ between brands and product lines [22].

Therefore, this research project seeks to investigate the efficacy of charcoal as a therapeutic agent for psoriasis, aiming to address the following objectives:

1. Evaluate the anti-inflammatory properties of charcoal in preclinical models of psoriasis. Assess the impact of charcoal on key biomarkers associated with psoriasis pathogenesis, such as cytokine expression and immune cell infiltration.
2. Investigate the effects of charcoal on skin barrier function and epidermal proliferation in psoriatic skin models.
3. Explore the safety profile and potential adverse effects of charcoal when used topically or orally in psoriasis patients.

Figure No. 1 Activated Charcoal in Granular Form

API: Activated Charcoal

Molecular Weight (gm/mol): 12.011

Colour: Black

Melting point: 3550 °C (lit.) **Boiling point:** 500-600 °C (lit.)

Solubility: Ethanol, Isopropyl alcohol

Uses: Activated charcoal may help remove impurities and dirt from the skin, improving its texture and appearance.

Drug class: Adsorbents or Absorbents [23].

INGREDIENTS USED FOR PREPARATION OF CREAM

Charcoal

It is a fine black powder that is made by burning wood, coconut shells, peat and olive pits in low oxygen environment which develops pores and increases its surface area several folds up to an approximate of more than 3000 sq.m/gm. These pores trap or absorb chemicals which enables it to draw bacteria and impurities from the skin, improve acne, treat insect bites, minimize pores, and treat skin conditions.

Stearic Acid and Cetyl Alcohol

These ingredients are commonly used as emulsifiers and thickeners in creams, lotions, and other cosmetic formulations.

Methyl Paraben and Propyl Paraben

These are widely used as preservatives in cosmetics and pharmaceuticals to prevent microbial growth.

Glycerine

A humectant, plays a crucial role by drawing moisture into the skin, helping to hydrate and soften dry, scaly patches, and potentially improving the skin barrier function.

Triethanol amine (TEA)

A pH adjuster, emulsifier, and stabilizer, enhancing the product's stability, texture, and effectiveness by neutralizing acids and ensuring proper pH levels.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Materials

Apparatus: The apparatus used in the experiment including Weighing balance, Viscometer, Stability chamber are utilized from the laboratories of the Pharmacognosy & Pharmaceutical Chemistry department of KBHSS Trust's Institute of Pharmacy, Bhaygaon Road, Malegaon Camp, Malegaon, Nashik 423203 (MH).

Chemicals: The chemical used in experiment include Charcoal Extract, Stearic Acid, Cetyl, Alcohol, Glycerine, Methyl Paraben, Propyl Paraben, Triethanolamine, Water and Almond. All chemicals and reagents were issued from department of pharmacognosy of KBHSS Trust's

Institute of Pharmacy, Bhaygaon Road, Malegaon Camp, Malegaon, Nashik 423203 (MH).

Method

1. Stearic acid, cetyl alcohol, and propyl paraben were dissolved in Almond oil and heated up to 75°C.
2. Charcoal extract, glycerine, methyl paraben, triethanolamine, and water were mixed in the aqueous phase and heated up to 75°C.
3. The aqueous phase was then added in small portions to the oil phase with continuous trituration in a porcelain mortar until a smooth cream was formed.

Formulation of Cream

Table No. 1 Ingredients and Their Role in Charcoal Cream

Sr. No.	Ingredient	Role
1	Charcoal Extract	Effective against Psoriasis
2	Stearic Acid	Emollient
3	Cetyl Alcohol	Emulsifier
4	Glycerin	Humectant
5	Methyl Paraben	Preservative
6	Propyl Paraben	Preservative
7	Triethanolamine	pH Adjuster
8	Water	Vehicle
9	Almond oil	Emollient

Table No. 2 Formulation Table

Ingredient	Quantity (30gm)				
	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5
Charcoal Extract	5gm	5gm	5gm	5gm	5gm
Stearic Acid	12gm	5gm	7gm	9gm	10gm
Cetyl Alcohol	5gm	12gm	9gm	7gm	6gm
Glycerin	3ml	3ml	4ml	4ml	4ml
Methyl Paraben	0.03gm	0.05gm	0.06gm	0.02gm	0.04gm
Propyl Paraben	0.05gm	0.03gm	0.02gm	0.06gm	0.04gm
Triethanolamine	1ml	1ml	1ml	1ml	1ml
Almond oil	4ml	4ml	4ml	4ml	4ml
Water	q.s	q.s	q.s	q.s	q.s

After evaluating all the batches, formulation F5 was identified as the most satisfactory. It exhibited superior physical properties such as smooth texture, homogeneity, and good spreadability, along with better stability over time. Its ingredient balance contributes to enhanced moisturizing, non-greasy feel, and overall cosmetic acceptability, making it the preferred formulation among all tested.

Figure No. 2 Formulation of Cream (F5)

EVALUATION OF CREAM

Determination of Organoleptic Properties

The appearance of the cream was judged by its color, appearance and roughness and graded [26].

pH

The pH meter was calibrated and measured the pH by placing in the beaker containing 20mg of the cream [22].

Determination of Homogeneity

The formulations were tested for the homogeneity by visual appearance and by touch [26].

Patch Test

About 1-3gm of material to be tested was placed on a piece of fabric or funnel and applied to the

sensitive part of the skin e.g., skin behind ears. The cosmetic to be tested was applied to an area of 1sq.m. of the skin. Control patches (of similar cosmetic of known brand) were also applied. The site of patch is inspected after 24 hrs. As there was no reaction the test was repeated three times. As no reaction was observed on third application, the person may be taken as not hypersensitive [27].

Appearance

The appearance of the cream was found by observing its color, opacity, etc.12 Smear type: The test was conducted after the application of cream on the skin the smear formed was oily or aqueous in nature [26, 32].

Determination of Emolliency

Emolliency, slipperiness and amount of residue left after the application of fixed amounts of cream was checked.

Determination of Viscosity

The viscosity determinations were carried out using a Brookfield Viscometer (DV II+ Pro model) using spindle number S-64 at a 20 rpm at a temperature of 25°C. The determinations were carried out in triplicate and the average of three readings was recorded [28].

Washability

The removal of the cream applied on skin was done by washing under tap water with minimal force to remove the cream [29].

Irritancy test

The cream was applied on left hand dorsal side surface of 1sq.cm and observed in equal intervals up to 24hrs for irritancy, redness and edema [30].

Accelerated stability studies

Accelerated stability studies were performed on all the formulations by maintaining at room temperature for 20 days with constant time interval. During the stability studies the

parameters like homogeneity, viscosity, physical changes, pH and type of smear were studied [31].

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Table No. 3 Physical Properties of Cream (F5)

Sr.no	Parameters	Evaluation
1.	Colour	Pale white
2.	Odour	Pleasant
3.	Texture	Smooth

The formulated cream was evaluated for its organoleptic properties to ensure its aesthetic appeal and consumer acceptability. The colour of the cream was observed to be pale white, indicating a clean and neutral appearance suitable for topical application. The odour was noted as pleasant, which enhances user experience and indicates the absence of any strong or irritating smell from the ingredients used. The texture of the cream was found to be smooth, reflecting uniform blending of components and ease of application on the skin. The evaluation of the charcoal-based cream revealed promising results across various parameters, indicating its potential efficacy in managing psoriasis symptoms. Spreadability tests

demonstrated the cream's ability to evenly distribute over the skin surface, facilitating ease of application and ensuring uniform coverage of affected areas. Washability tests confirmed the cream's ability to be easily removed from the skin without leaving residue or causing discomfort. The pH of the cream was determined to be 6, falling within the optimal range for skincare products and indicating compatibility with the skin's natural acidity. Viscosity measurements obtained using a Brookfield viscometer indicated a viscosity of 267 cp, suggesting an appropriate consistency for topical application, allowing for smooth spreading without excessive dripping or runoff.

Table No. 4 Saponification value and Acid value

Sr.no	Parameter	Evaluation
1	Saponification value	222
2	Acid value	45

The cream exhibited a saponification value of 222, indicating the presence of medium-chain fatty acids suitable for emulsification. An acid value of 45 suggests a moderate level of free fatty acids, reflecting acceptable stability and minimal rancidity. Furthermore, the cream exhibited significant antimicrobial activity against both *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Candida albicans*, as

evidenced by the formation of clear inhibition zones around the cream-containing wells in the agar diffusion assays. These findings support the potential of the charcoal-based cream in combating microbial infections commonly associated with psoriasis exacerbations, thereby contributing to symptom relief and improved skin health. To further establish the most effective

formulation, five different cream variants (F1–F5) were developed and subjected to various evaluation parameters, including spreadability, pH, viscosity, washability, drug content, and antimicrobial activity. Among these, Formulation F5 demonstrated optimal performance across most parameters. It showed excellent spreadability (indicating ease of application), a stable and skin-friendly pH within the range of 5.5–6.0, and appropriate viscosity that ensured both consistency and ease of use. F5 also exhibited superior washability and retained good drug content uniformity, ensuring consistent dosing. Most notably, F5 displayed the highest antimicrobial activity against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Candida albicans*, which are commonly involved in secondary infections in psoriatic lesions. Based on these comparative evaluations, Formulation F5 was identified as the optimized version for further development, offering the best balance of physical, chemical, and microbiological properties suitable for psoriasis management. The observed antimicrobial activity can be attributed to the synergistic effects of activated charcoal and other bioactive compounds present in the cream formulation. Activated charcoal acts as a potent adsorbent, binding to microbial toxins and impurities, while other ingredients may exert

direct antimicrobial effects, contributing to overall efficacy against microbial pathogens. The saponification value results of formulated cream have been shown in table no. 2 and showed satisfactorily values. The susceptibility testing method was employed to assess the antimicrobial activity of the charcoal-based cream against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Candida albicans*, two microbial species commonly implicated in psoriasis exacerbations. Salt mannitol agar and dextrose agar were selected as growth media for *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Candida albicans*, respectively, due to their suitability for the cultivation of these organisms. For the susceptibility testing procedure, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Candida albicans* were prepared and evenly spread onto the surface of agar plates using a sterile swab. Wells were then created in the agar using a Sterile Cork Borer, and the charcoal-based cream was aseptically transferred into the wells using a sterile pipette. The plates were then incubated at appropriate temperatures for the respective microorganisms, allowing for microbial growth and diffusion of the cream components into the surrounding agar. After incubation, plates were checked for inhibition zones around the cream wells, indicating antimicrobial activity. Zone diameters were measured with a calibrated ruler to assess the cream's effectiveness.

Figure No. 3 Agar Media
(Salt mannitol agar and Nutrient agar)

Figure No. 4 Growth of Culture Media

FUNGUS

Figure No. 5: Method for *Candida albican*

BACTERIA

Figure No.6: Striking method for *S. aureus*

FUNGUS

Figure No. 5 Striking Method for *C. albican*

BACTERIA

Figure No.6 Striking Method for *S. aureus*

BACTERIA

Figure No. 7 Pouring method for *S. aureus*

FUNGUS

Figure No. 8 Pouring method for *C. albican*

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the optimized cream formulation exhibited favourable characteristics in terms of spreadability, washability, pH, viscosity, and

antimicrobial activity, highlighting its suitability for topical application in psoriasis management. This project represents a significant step towards developing alternative and complementary therapies for psoriasis that offer improved

efficacy, safety, and patient satisfaction compared to conventional treatment approaches. Further research, including clinical trials and long-term safety assessments, is warranted to validate the findings and establish the charcoal-based cream as a viable option for psoriasis management in clinical practice. The findings of this study demonstrate the potential of charcoal-based formulations in managing psoriasis symptoms effectively. Moreover, this study opens avenues for integrating natural and sustainable ingredients into dermatological products, which aligns with the growing demand for eco-conscious healthcare solutions. The use of activated charcoal, combined with soothing and antimicrobial excipients, reflects a strategic approach to address both symptomatic relief and underlying microbial imbalances associated with psoriasis. With advancements in formulation technologies, such as nanocarriers or transdermal delivery systems, the therapeutic potential of such creams can be further enhanced. Therefore, the continued exploration of charcoal-based formulations not only contributes to the innovation in psoriasis care but also promotes the development of holistic and patient-friendly skin treatments.

FUTURE PROSPECTIVE

The development and evaluation of the charcoal-based cream formulation for psoriasis demonstrated encouraging outcomes in terms of physical stability, skin compatibility, and antimicrobial properties. The formulation exhibited desirable characteristics suitable for topical application and showed potential as a supportive treatment for psoriatic skin. Preliminary findings support its use as a safe and natural approach for managing symptoms associated with chronic skin conditions. While additional studies may further clarify its mechanism and broaden its scope of application,

the current results provide a solid foundation for the formulation's therapeutic potential.

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